

ERNEST HEMINGUEY ASARLARINI O'RGANISHDA ADIB BIOGRAFIYASINING
O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola Amerika adabiyotining yirik vakili Ernest Heminguey ijodini o'rganishda uning hayot yo'lining tutgan o'rni va ahamiyatini tahlil qiladi. Maqolada yozuvchining shaxsiy tajribasi, hayotiy voqealari va biografik faktlarining uning badiiy asarlariga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatganligi ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, biografik yondashuv orqali Heminguey prozasining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, uslubiy jihatlari va mavzuviy yo'nalishlari ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ernest Heminguey, biografiya, adabiy tahlil, Amerika adabiyoti, biografik yondashuv, hayot va ijod.

THE ROLE OF THE WRITER'S BIOGRAPHY IN THE STUDY OF ERNEST
HEMINGWAY'S WORKS

Abstract. This article analyzes the role and significance of the life path of Ernest Hemingway, a major representative of American literature, in the study of his work. The article examines how the writer's personal experience, life events, and biographical facts influenced his works of art. The work reveals the specific features, stylistic aspects, and thematic directions of Hemingway's prose through a biographical approach. The study proves that the writer's biography is of great importance for a full understanding of his creative heritage.

Keywords: Ernest Hemingway, biography, literary analysis, American literature, biographical approach, life and work.

KIRISH

XX asr Amerika adabiyotida alohida o'rin tutgan Ernest Miller Heminguey (1899-1961) nafaqat o'zining noyob yozuv uslubi, balki hayotining dramatik voqealari bilan ham keng tanilgan. Uning ijodini o'rganishda biografik yondashuv alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi, chunki yozuvchining shaxsiy tajribasi va hayotiy voqealari uning asarlarida bevosita aks etgan¹.

Heminguey ijodini tadqiq etuvchi olimlar uzoq vaqtdan beri yozuvchining hayoti va ijodi o'rtasidagi zich bog'liqlikni ta'kidlab kelmoqdalar. Uning romanlarida va hikoyalarida aks etgan voqealar ko'pincha avtobiografik xarakterga ega bo'lib, adibning shaxsiy kechinmalari va tajribalari asosida yaratilgan².

Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi Heminguey asarlarini to'la va chuqur tushunish uchun uning biografiasini o'rganishning qanchalik zarurligini isbotlash hamda adib hayotining ijodiy jarayonlarga ta'sirini aniqlashdan iborat.

¹ Baker, Carlos. "Ernest Hemingway: A Life Story". New York: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1969, p. 45.

² Reynolds, Michael. "Hemingway: The Paris Years". Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1989, p. 78.

ASOSIY QISM

Adib hayot yo'lining uning ijodga ta'siri

Ernest Heminguey 1899-yil 21-iyulda Oak Park shahridagi (Illinoys shtati) o'rta sinf oilasida tug'ilgan. Otasi Klarens Edmund Heminguey shifokor, onasi Greys Hall Heminguey musiqa o'qituvchisi edi³. Bolalik yillari va oilaviy muhit yozuvchining kelajakdagi ijodiy yo'nalishiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

Heminguey hayotidagi eng muhim bosqichlardan biri Birinchi jahon urushiga qatnashishi bo'ldi. 1918-yilda u Italiyaning shimolida harbiy shifokor sifatida xizmat qildi va og'ir yaralandi⁴. Bu tajriba uning "Alvido, qurol" (A Farewell to Arms, 1929) romanining asosi bo'ldi. Urush davridagi kechinmalar va ko'rgan azob-uqubatlar Heminguey prozasining asosiy mavzularidan birini - urush fojeasini - shakllantirishda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynadi.

Biografiya va badiiy uslub o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik

Heminguey uslubining o'ziga xos jihatlari - qisqa, aniq jumlar, sodda lug'at, dialoqlarning ustunligi - uning gazetachilik faoliyati bilan bevosita bog'liq⁵. 1920-yillarning boshida u Kansas City Star gazetasida ishlagani ma'lum. Gazetachilik tajribasi unga aniq va qisqa ifoda usulini o'rgatdi, bu keyinchalik uning badiiy asarlarining ajralmas qismiga aylandi.

Parij yillari (1921-1926) Heminguey ijodida alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu davrda u "yo'qolgan avlod"ning vakillari - Gertrude Stein, Ezra Pound, Skott Fitzgerald kabi yozuvchilar bilan yaqin muloqotda bo'ldi⁶. Parij muhiti va shu davrdagi kechinmalar uning "Quyosh chiqadi" (The Sun Also Rises, 1926) romanining asosini tashkil etdi.

Biografik elementlarning asarlardagi aksi

Heminguey asarlarida avtobiografik elementlar deyarli barcha asarlarida uchraydi. "Alvido, qurol" romanidagi Frederik Henry obrazi ko'p jihatdan yozuvchining o'zini eslatadi - ikkalasi ham urushda yaralangan, ikkalasi ham hamshira bilan sevisgan⁷

"Qo'ng'iroq kimning motamini chalayotir" (For Whom the Bell Tolls, 1940) romanini yozishdan oldin Heminguey Ispaniya fuqarolar urushida (1936-1939) jurnalist sifatida qatnashgan ekanligi ma'lum.⁸ Bu tajriba romandagi voqealar va personajlarning hayotiyiligini ta'minlagan omillardan biri bo'lib hisoblanadi.

Tabiat va sport mavzularining biografik kelib chiqishi

Heminguey asarlarida tabiat tasviri va sport mavzulari muhim o'rin tutadi. Bu uning bolalikdan boshlab ota bilan baliq tutish va ov qilishga qiziqishi bilan bog'liq⁹. "Chol va dengiz" (The Old Man and the Sea, 1952) qissasi yozuvchining Kuba dengizida baliq tutish tajribasi asosida yaratilgan.

³ Griffin, Peter. "Along with Youth: Hemingway, The Early Years". New York: Oxford University Press, 1985, p. 23.

⁴ Hemingway, Ernest. "Selected Letters 1917-1961". Ed. Carlos Baker. New York: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1981, p. 156.

⁵ Fenton, Charles A. "The Apprenticeship of Ernest Hemingway: The Early Years". New York: Farrar, Straus and Young, 1954, p. 89.

⁶ Beach, Sylvia. "Shakespeare and Company". New York: Harcourt, Brace and Company, 1959, p. 201.

⁷ Young, Philip. "Ernest Hemingway: A Reconsideration". University Park: Pennsylvania State University Press, 1966, p. 134.

⁸ Meyers, Jeffrey. "Hemingway: A Biography". New York: Harper & Row, 1985, p. 298.

⁹ Sanford, Marcelline Hemingway. "At the Hemingways: A Family Portrait". Boston: Little, Brown and Company, 1962, p. 67.

Yozuvchining buqa jangiga bo'lgan qiziqishi "Quyosh hiqadi" va "Peshindan keyingi o'lim" (Death in the Afternoon, 1932) asarlarida o'z aksini topgan. Heminguey bu sport turini hayot va o'lim kurashi timsoli sifatida talqin etgan¹⁰.

Afrikaning yashil tepaliklari" (Green Hills of Africa, 1935) asari Heminguey biografiyasining bevosita aks etgan noyob namunalardan biridir. 1933-1934 yillarda yozuvchi rafiqasi Pauline bilan birga Kenyada safari qilgan va bu tajriba asarning to'g'ridan-to'g'ri manbai bo'lgan¹¹. Kitobda Heminguey o'zini "yozuvchi" sifatida tasvirlaydi va haqiqiy voqealarni badiiy shaklda qayta yaratadi. Yozuvchining o'zi "bu kitobda hech narsa o'ylab topilmagan" deb ta'kidlagan¹². Asarda yozuvchining safari davridagi kundalik hayoti, ov jarayonlari, Afrika tabiatiga bo'lgan hayrati va mahalliy aholi bilan muloqoti batafsil tasvirlangan. Heminguey bu asarda o'zining yozuvchilik san'ati haqidagi fikrlarini ham bayon etgan, buni uning quyidagi fikrlari orqali bilib olish mumkin: "Yaxshi yozuvchi doimo chinakam narsani yozishga harakat qilishi kerak"¹³. Afrika safari tajribasi uning kelajakdagi "Kilimanjaro qorlari" (The Snows of Kilimanjaro, 1936) va "Makombening qisqa baxtli hayoti" (The Short Happy Life of Francis Macomber, 1936) hikoyalarining ham asosini tashkil etdi.

Shaxsiy munosabatlar va badiiy personajlar

Hemingueyning shaxsiy munosabatlari, turmush yo'lidagi o'zgarishlar, har bir nikohi uning ijodiga o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatgan. Birinchi rafiqasi Hedli Richardson bilan munosabatlari "Paris - moveable feast" (A Moveable Feast, 1964) kitobida batafsil tasvirlangan¹⁴. Uchinchi rafiqasi Marta Gelhorn bilan urush yillarida birga bo'lishi "Qo'ng'iroq kimning motamini chalayotir" romanidagi Maria obrazining yaratilishiga ta'sir ko'rsatgan bo'lsa, to'rtinchi rafiqasi Mary Welsh bilan bo'lgan hayoti "Chol va dengiz" povestining yozilishi davriga to'g'ri keladi¹⁵. Bundan xulosa qilib aytish mumkinki, yozuvchi hayotidagi munosabatlar uning asarlariga, yozish uslubiga o'z ta'sirini o'tkazmasdan qolmaydi.

Kasallik va ijodiy inqiroz

Heminguey hayotining so'nggi yillarida ruhiy va jismoniy kasalliklari uning ijodiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatdi. 1950-yillarning oxirida yozuvchi depressiya va alkogolizmdan aziyat chekdi¹⁶. Bu holat uning oxirgi asarlarining sifatiga ta'sir qildi va ijodiy qobiliyatining susayishiga olib keldi. 1961-yil 2-iyulda Heminguey o'z joniga qasd qildi. Bu fojiali voqea uning ijodiy merosini yangicha qirradan baholashga majbur etdi. Ko'plab tanqidchilar uning hayotining dramatik yakunini ijodiy inqirozning natijasi deb baholashadi¹⁷.

¹⁰ Mandel, Miriam B. "Reading Hemingway: The Facts in the Fictions". Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow Press, 1995, p. 245.

¹¹ Hemingway, Ernest. "Green Hills of Africa". New York: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1935, foreword.

¹² Shumway, Donald R. "Hemingway's Green Hills of Africa as Evolutionary Narrative." "The Hemingway Review", vol. 15, no. 1, 1995, p. 57.

¹³ Mandel, Miriam B. "Reading Hemingway: The Facts in the Fictions". Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow Press, 1995, p. 245.

¹⁴ Diliberto, Gioia. "Paris Without End: The True Story of Hemingway's First Wife". New York: HarperCollins, 2011, p. 187.

¹⁵ Kerr, Bernice. "The Hemingway Women". New York: W.W. Norton & Company, 1983, p. 432.

¹⁶ Lynn, Kenneth S. "Hemingway". New York: Simon and Schuster, 1987, p. 578.

¹⁷ Hotchner, A.E. "Papa Hemingway: A Personal Memoir". New York: Random House, 1966, p. 289.

XULOSA

Ernest Heminguey ijodini o'rganishda biografik yondashuvning ahamiyati shubhasizdir. Yozuvchining hayot tajribasi, shaxsiy kechinmalari va voqealari uning badiiy asarlarining manbai bo'lib xizmat qilgan.

Urush tajribasi, gazetachilik faoliyati, sayohatlar, shaxsiy munosabatlar - bularning barchasi Heminguey prozasining shaklanishida muhim rol o'ynagan. Biografik tahlil orqali biz Heminguey asarlarining chuqur ma'nolarini, personajlarining psixologiyasini va yozuvchining ijodiy metodlarini yanada yaxshi tushuna olamiz.

Uning "aysberg nazariyasi" - matnda ko'rinadigan qism butun ma'noning faqat sakkizdan bir qismini tashkil etishi haqidagi g'oyasi ham yozuvchining hayotiy tajribasi bilan chambarchas bog'liq.

Heminguey misolida ko'ramizki, yirik adibning biografiyasini o'rganmasdan turib, uning ijodiy merosini to'la qamrab olish va baholash deyarli mumkin emas. Hayot va ijod o'rtasidagi dialektik bog'liqlik adabiy tadqiqotlarning muhim tamoyillaridan biri sifatida namoyon bo'ladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Baker, Carlos. "Ernest Hemingway: A Life Story". New York: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1969, p. 45.
2. Reynolds, Michael. "Hemingway: The Paris Years". Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1989, p. 78.
3. Griffin, Peter. "Along with Youth: Hemingway, The Early Years". New York: Oxford University Press, 1985, p. 23.
4. Hemingway, Ernest. "Selected Letters 1917-1961". Ed. Carlos Baker. New York: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1981, p. 156.
5. Fenton, Charles A. "The Apprenticeship of Ernest Hemingway: The Early Years". New York: Farrar, Straus and Young, 1954, p. 89.
6. Beach, Sylvia. "Shakespeare and Company". New York: Harcourt, Brace and Company, 1959, p. 201.
7. Young, Philip. "Ernest Hemingway: A Reconsideration". University Park: Pennsylvania State University Press, 1966, p. 134.
8. Meyers, Jeffrey. "Hemingway: A Biography". New York: Harper & Row, 1985, p. 298.
9. Sanford, Marcelline Hemingway. "At the Hemingways: A Family Portrait". Boston: Little, Brown and Company, 1962, p. 67.
10. Hemingway, Ernest. "Green Hills of Africa". New York: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1935, foreword.
11. Shumway, Donald R. "Hemingway's Green Hills of Africa as Evolutionary Narrative." "The Hemingway Review", vol. 15, no. 1, 1995, p. 57.
12. Hemingway, Ernest. "Green Hills of Africa". New York: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1935, p. 27.
13. Mandel, Miriam B. "Reading Hemingway: The Facts in the Fictions". Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow Press, 1995, p. 245.

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14. Diliberto, Gioia. "Paris Without End: The True Story of Hemingway's First Wife". New York: HarperCollins, 2011, p. 187.
15. Kerr, Bernice. "The Hemingway Women". New York: W.W. Norton & Company, 1983, p. 432.
16. Lynn, Kenneth S. "Hemingway". New York: Simon and Schuster, 1987, p. 578.
17. Hotchner, A.E. "Papa Hemingway: A Personal Memoir". New York: Random House, 1966, p. 289.

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